

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE CONTRIBUTION OF AZERBAIJAN'S NATIONAL LEADER HEYDAR ALIYEV TO ISRAEL-AZERBAIJAN RELATIONS

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Abstract

Azerbaijan began to draw the attention of the Jewish elite since 1810 and in 1832 the first synagogue was built in Baku. During the first term of the presidency of the National Leader Heydar Aliyev, Azerbaijani-Israeli relations turned into a strategic partnership and made significant progress. National leader Heydar Aliyev has an extraordinary role in the formation and development of relations between Israel and Azerbaijan. Stressing that Azerbaijan is a peaceful and multi-ethnic country, Heydar Aliyev said that Jews have lived here in peace and kindness with Azerbaijanis for centuries: "Jews have lived together with Azerbaijanis in Azerbaijan for centuries, in a framework of friendship and kindness. Even today, Jews are citizens of Azerbaijan with full equal rights, and Azerbaijan is their homeland. All these create great opportunities for our cooperation."

Keywords: Heydar Aliyev, Azerbaijan, Israel, friendship, peaceful country.

During the rule of Azerbaijan's National Leader Heydar Aliyev, relations with Israel held significant importance in Azerbaijan's foreign policy. He emphasized that the coexistence of various ethnic and religious groups, including Jews, in peace and harmony was an important part of the country's cultural diversity. Under his leadership, these principles were strengthened, and the rights of various ethnic groups were always protected. In this context, relations with Israel were particularly noteworthy. It was during Heydar Aliyev's tenure that official diplomatic relations between Azerbaijan and Israel were established, leading to positive outcomes in trade and economic relations, cultural and educational exchanges, security and defense cooperation, political and diplomatic support between the countries, as well as strategic partnership. Notably, during Heydar Aliyev's time, trade relations between the two countries were considerably high, and Israel became one of the interested partners in Azerbaijan's economic development and energy sector.

During the first presidency of Azerbaijan's national leader Heydar Aliyev (1993-1998), Azerbaijan-Israel relations evolved into a strategic partnership and developed to a high level. It is worth noting that between 1992 and 1995, Israel-Azerbaijan cooperation was cautious and often informal, as both countries existed in a "diplomatic vacuum."¹ [8].

The first official meeting between the two countries took place in December 1993 during the official visit of Israeli Deputy Efraim Sneh² to Azerbaijan. He had announced this during his return visit to Azerbaijan on December 4, 1999, in his capacity as Israel's Deputy Minister of Defense and Co-Chair of the US-Israel-Azerbaijan Parliamentary Joint Group. In his statement,

Sneh expressed Israel's interest in developing economic and cultural relations with Azerbaijan. He also mentioned his satisfaction with the warm reception and friendly relations extended by the Azerbaijani people to the Jewish community living in Azerbaijan, both now and in the past, and noted that this was highly valued in his country [3].

The Israeli Embassy in Baku was opened on August 29, 1993. Eliezer Yotvat, who served as Israel's first Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary to Azerbaijan from 1993 to 1996, presented his credentials to Heydar Aliyev on March 22, 1994, at the start of his diplomatic mission. Yotvat made considerable efforts to elevate bilateral relations to the highest level. During his tenure, he worked to promote the development of relations between the two countries and aimed to enhance cooperation in various fields [7]. Although the Israeli Embassy was established in Azerbaijan in 1992, Azerbaijan's embassy in Israel was only opened approximately 30 years later, on March 29, 2023. The current Azerbaijani Ambassador to Israel is Mukhtar Mammadov [6].

The development of relations between the two countries has been significantly influenced by meetings and visits between the heads of state of Israel and Azerbaijan. For instance, during this period, the national leader Heydar Aliyev met with Israeli officials at various events and discussed issues of mutual interest. Between 1999 and 2014, there were 28 diplomatic and official exchanges of significant state importance between the two countries. These visits involved official representatives in the fields of agriculture, economic development, medicine, transportation, and tourism. [1, p.15].

¹ This term is used in international relations and diplomacy to describe a situation where there is a lack of diplomatic relations or influence in a particular region or on a specific issue.

² Efraim Sneh is an Israeli politician, physician, and a retired Brigadier General in the Israel Defense Forces. He served as

a member of the Knesset from the Labor Party between 1992 and 2008 and held several ministerial positions. Efraim Sneh has worked as Israel's Minister of Defense, Minister of Health, and in various other political and military roles. He is also one of the individuals who contributed to the development of relations between Israel and Azerbaijan.

If we list these visits and meetings sequentially, we can note the following:

- On January 28, 1995, Heydar Aliyev met with then-Israeli Foreign Minister Shimon Peres at the World Economic Forum held in Switzerland.

- On October 22, 1995, he met with Israeli Prime Minister Yitzhak Rabin during the United Nations General Assembly session.

- On December 2, 1996, he met with Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu at the OSCE summit of heads of state in Lisbon.

- On January 11, 1997, he met with then-Israeli Prime Minister Shimon Peres at the funeral of former President of France François Mitterrand.

On August 29, 1997, Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu made a short visit to Azerbaijan and met with President Heydar Aliyev. During this meeting, it was decided to establish a working group to enhance cooperation between the two countries [2]. This visit was recorded as the first visit of an Israeli Prime Minister to Baku [4, p.70].

Meetings between Heydar Aliyev and Benjamin Netanyahu have significantly impacted the strengthening and expansion of relations between Azerbaijan and Israel. These meetings have promoted the development of cooperation in economic, security, and strategic fields between the two countries, as well as helped protect mutual interests at the international level.

The meetings between the National Leader Heydar Aliyev and Israeli officials played a crucial role in the development of diplomatic and strategic relations between the two countries. These meetings aimed to strengthen Azerbaijan's relations with Israel and increase cooperation across various fields. Heydar Aliyev's official visit to Israel in 1996 included a meeting with then-Israeli Prime Minister Shimon Peres. During this visit, discussions were held on cooperation between Azerbaijan and Israel in various areas, including economics, security, and technology.

On May 6, 2010, during the inauguration ceremony of the boulevard named after the national leader of the Azerbaijan, Heydar Aliyev, in the city of Hadera, Israel, the Mayor of Hadera, Haim Avinat, remarked that Heydar Aliyev, the founder of independent Azerbaijan, is remembered in world history as a just and humane head of state. He highlighted that Aliyev made no distinctions among the nations in Azerbaijan, and as a

result, Azerbaijan is recognized as one of the most tolerant countries in the world [5, p.253-254].

Today, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan successfully continues the historical traditions established by the National Leader Heydar Aliyev.

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